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Abstract: This article talks about the role and development of mass media in our society.

Key words: mass media, public information, journalism, internet, internet network, websites.

If you look at the 32-year history of independent Uzbekistan, you can see the great changes achieved in the information policy. Legal reforms aimed at ensuring freedom of speech, information and the press in Uzbekistan began in the early years of independence.

In particular, between 1991 and 2002, "On mass media", "On guarantees and freedom of information", "On information dissemination", "Principles and guarantees of freedom of information" The adoption of the most important sectoral laws, such as the Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan on "Protection of Journalistic Activity", was achieved.

In the past period, legislation related to the field was gradually improved, several important decrees and decisions related to the information field, state programs were adopted by the President. Especially in the last 5-6 years, the issues of expanding mass media and journalistic and blogging activities, creating equal conditions for information participants in the media market have risen to a new level. Many foreign mass media have been accredited in Uzbekistan, and a legal basis has been created for their free activity in the country.

In the next seven years, the number of mass media in our country increased from 1,514 to 2,140 due to special attention to the sector, created privileges and opportunities. 65 percent of them are contributed by the private sector. Of these, 1255

are newspapers and magazines, 18 are newsletters. 116 of them are television and radio channels, and the number of Internet publications has increased from 395 to 745. So, the number of Internet publications alone has increased to 350.

Ensuring freedom of speech and information openness cannot be achieved without developing the national information space and information infrastructure. For this purpose, in the years of independence, significant work was done to create a convenient infrastructure for mass media in our country.

In particular, about 118 km across Uzbekistan. length of optical fiber communication lines were laid, the number of mobile communication base stations was increased to 49,640. As a result, the price of 1 Mbit/s Internet connection for providers has been reduced from 422.27 US dollars in 2013 to about 3 US dollars. The total number of Internet users has exceeded 27 million. The throughput capacity of the international data transmission network has reached 1,800 Gbit/s.

Taking into account the needs and wishes of people of many nationalities living in our republic, print media are published in 12 languages, this practice is also used in television and radio, broadcasts and shows are broadcast in Russian and English languages, in addition to the languages of the brotherly nations. , websites operate in Uzbek, Russian and English languages.

Today, mass media in our republic have covered political-social, legal, medical, educational, women's, social-educational, economic-social, sports, spiritual-educational, and many similar fields. Along with mass media of state and public organizations, a number of organizations aimed at supporting non-state mass media and their activities have been created.

In order to inform the international community about the life of our country, the achievements made in the implementation of reforms, to satisfy the population's need for information, and to strengthen the interaction between citizens and state bodies, there are almost websites of all government bodies are posted. It should be noted that the number of websites other than the websites of state bodies is also increasing. In particular, the number of websites in the "Uz" domain zone increased from 587 in 2002 to 10 thousand websites registered in the national Internet space in February 2010, and as of June 2015, their number reached 21.86 thousand. As a result of the consistent introduction of modern technologies into the industry, completely new media structures such as digital, mobile and Internet television are entering the system. There are electronic versions of about 200 publications in the global network. Also, computerization centers in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Navoi, Namangan, Fergana and Samarkand regions have been given the status of registering the domain "Uz". This

serves to register the "uz" domain in the regions themselves and further increase their number.

The increasing number of websites creates opportunities not only for our citizens, but also for other countries to get full information about the reforms being carried out in our Republic.

The world community, which has entered the informational stage of development in the 21st century, is on the path of modernization and informatization of all areas. The revolutionary impact of information and communication technologies is observed in state structures and institutions of civil society, economic and social sphere, science and education, culture and people's lifestyle. Computer technologies give people the opportunity to use their potential more fully, help them achieve the goals of increasing the level of well-being, strengthening democracy, peace and stability.

These examples show that the policy of mass media liberalization in our country is being implemented on a systematic basis, step by step and focused on specific goals. At the same time, the reforms implemented in various spheres of social life in our country ultimately led to the emergence of new directions in the work of mass media and the improvement of the legislative framework related to the sphere.

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